

BMET5933 ASSIGNMENT 2

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1. INTRODUCTION

Pneumonia is a type of respiratory infection caused by virus, bacteria or fungi, which causes alveoli of the lungs to fill with fluid [1]. In children, it is the leading infectious cause of death worldwide, responsible for approximately 14% of all deaths of children under five years of age, claiming an estimated 740,180 lives in 2019 alone [2]. While diagnostic tools such as auscultation to count breaths per minute, pulse oximetry and blood testing (CBC) are common, chest X-ray (CXR) imaging is widely used to observe inflation in lungs [3,4]. Additionally, computed tomography (CT), lung ultrasound (LUS) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) are utilized in complicated pneumonia [5]. However, such facilities are not always available in low-resource countries, and even if accessible, CXR's inability to clearly distinguish between viral and bacterial pneumonia, inter-observer variability, diagnostic subjectivity and high dose of radiation pose challenges [4,5]. Therefore limited resource settings demand for scalable, accurate, and rapid diagnostic methods, which has turned attention towards artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML) or deep learning (DL) for biomedical image analysis [6].

ML and DL models as a part of computer aided diagnostic (CAD) systems are being widely tested to aid in diagnosis of pneumonia as they enable recognition of patterns and differentiate between subtle differences more effectively than human senses in CXRs, CT and MRI thus, supplementing clinicians in decision making [7]. Typically, a sequential functioning of CAD involves processing input data, extracting features using Gaussian filters, morphological operations and edge detection and lastly classifying using suitable classifier such as random forest, convolutional neural networks (CNNs) or using transfer learning models like ResNet50 [8].

Notably, the Random Forest model developed by Fazal M. et. al. on a GitHub Covid-19 dataset had a resulting accuracy of 82.29% with significant precision and recall capabilities, demonstrating potential for robust pneumonia classification [9]. Similarly, Xun Z. et. al. also utilized random forest algorithms and key

biomarkers on a set of clinical and laboratory data from 214 patients for 3 class classification and achieved

overall model accuracy of 77%, which further validates the potential of machine learning techniques for more targeted and effective diagnosis [10]. Some other studies, like the one by Okeke S. et. al. have built CNN from scratch consisting of 4 convolutional layers and MaxPooling layers then dropout and 2 dense layers with a ReLu activator in between [11]. Despite the lack of data, this model achieved a remarkable validation accuracy indicating that CNN models could help mitigate the reliability and interpretability

challenge of biomedical images [11]. Furthermore, Choudhary et. al. utilized popular transfer learning methodology and designed eight different deep learning pre trained CNNs for three-class classification on a dataset of 3487 CXR images, which achieved an accuracy of 97.74% by CheXNet with 96.61% sensitivity, precision and F1 score and 98.31% specificity [12]. Similarly, Barath N. et. al. proposed a novel transfer learning approach using ResNet50 on an imbalanced and limited training dataset, and were able to achieve 89.06% overall accuracy with an F1 score of 87% using enhanced hold out validation [13]. This study serves as a proof of concept that automated detection approaches can surpass the barrier of limited and imbalanced datasets and shows immense potential for biomedical imaging analysis [13].

While these advancements are significant, some limitations still exist. For instance most models struggled with high dimensional data with few variables, and also lacked generalizability across populations and hospitals, as they were trained on limited and biased datasets and were dependent on specific features [9-13]. A lack of implicit feature extraction leads to the model being dependent on robust feature extraction. Complex models like deep neural networks have many hidden layers which allows for complex pattern recognition and final decision making. This process makes DL black box models which lack explainability, making them difficult for clinicians to trust [14]. Real-world deployments often

encounter unexpected issues like infrastructure limitations, besides patient history and socio-economic factors which also affect the actual outcome and thus, limits usability [15]. Additionally, regulatory frameworks are not yet equipped to certify adaptive, learning-based systems, and ethical concerns around data privacy and decision transparency remain unresolved [16].

This study, aims to train and test three models viz-Random forest, CNN from scratch and Transfer Learning model using ResNet50 on pediatric pneumonia chest x-ray dataset for 3-class classification which enhances clinical relevance (normal, viral pneumonia and bacterial pneumonia), unlike binary classification. In view of the limitations expressed in the current state of art, we further compare and contrast our three models to the literature. Thus, our study lays the groundwork for deploying AI systems in clinical triage workflows to accelerate diagnosis and reduce mortality among children with respiratory illnesses.

2. TECHNICAL CONTRIBUTION

2.1 Dataset

For this study, we used pediatric chest X-ray images from the publicly available dataset introduced by Kermany et al. in “Identifying Medical Diagnoses and Treatable Diseases by Image-Based Deep Learning” [17]. While the full dataset includes both OCT and chest X-ray images, we focused solely on the 5856 pediatric chest X-rays. The training set consists of 5232 images (2538 bacterial pneumonia, 1345 viral pneumonia, and 1349 normal), and the test set contains 624 images (242 bacterial, 148 viral, and 234 normal). Originally, the dataset grouped all pneumonia cases together, but we manually reclassified them into bacterial and viral categories to improve preprocessing, enable targeted model training, and facilitate 3 class evaluation. Using all available data ensures better generalization, which is especially important in medical imaging where annotated datasets are limited.

2.2 Exploratory Data Analysis and Pre Processing

For Exploratory Data Analysis we first visualized our class distributions to find that there were 1349 Normal, 1345 Viral and 2538 Bacterial Images in the Training dataset. Bacterial class was almost twice as large as Normal and Viral class, suggesting highly imbalanced data, as is clear in Figure 1.

Fig 1: Class Distribution Graph

Next, we visualized the pixel intensity distributions of the three classes using intensity histograms shown in Figure 2. The analysis revealed that images in the normal class contained significantly fewer high-intensity (brighter) pixels compared to those in the viral and bacterial pneumonia classes. This contrast in brightness patterns provides a useful visual cue that can assist our models in effectively distinguishing between the classes. However, one must be careful while using pixel intensity features for classification, because it could also lead to a biased model. Hence, if utilizing manual feature extraction techniques for training models, a balance must be maintained.

Fig 2: Pixel Intensity Distribution

All images were resized to 256×256 size to ensure uniformity, as CNN models require consistent input dimensions. For the transfer learning model using ResNet50, 224x224 image size was selected, as it is a core requirement of the model. The dataset was then split into training, validation, and test sets in a 60:20:20 ratio, with images loaded in batches of 50. To optimize training performance and reduce data loading bottlenecks, we employed prefetching, which allows the data pipeline to prepare the next batch while the current one is being processed [18]. Additional preprocessing techniques such as image augmentation and class

weighting were selectively applied to specific models to address data imbalance and improve generalization. These methods are discussed in detail under the technical contributions of each classifier.

2.3 CNN Classifier - CHAHAT

Convolutional Neural Networks is a subclass of Artificial Neural Networks which have gained popularity in image based classifications like chest x-ray classification [19]. CNNs automatically learn features from input images via backpropagation to extract hierarchical patterns from images, making them highly effective for visual recognition tasks, like those in radiological applications [19]. CNN’s hold a promising future for radiological applications, however limitations still exist, specifically those regarding limited dataset and overfitting issues [19].

Our lightweight CNN classifier was built from scratch to tackle these limitations, utilizing supervised learning which would enhance interpretability and require less computational power as compared to DL or transfer learning models. Limited data and overfitting issue was handled using image augmentation technique, which synthetically increases the size and generalizability of the training dataset by applying random rotation, random translation and random zoom [20].

Next, class weights were calculated to balance the training because of a highly imbalanced dataset. Class weights is a commonly used method which assigns higher weights to minority classes and lower weights to majority class, to avoid biased training of the model [21]. For bacterial class the weights came out to be 0.6872, while for normal and viral classes it was higher - 1.2928 and 1.2967 respectively, which aligns with the class count conducted during EDA.

Moreover, our CNN classifier’s architecture begins with an input layer which accepts images of size - (256,256,3). Since, our neural network is less complex we could use larger size for input images, which allowed for less deformation, more finer feature extraction and a balanced computational efficiency [22]. Next, the input images get normalized by (1.0/255) to ensure consistency in pixel intensity. Our model had 4 convolutional layers (Conv2D) with increasing filter depths (32 → 32 → 64 → 128), which enabled the network to learn a richer set of features as the feature

complexity increases and spatial dimensions are reduced [23]. Each Conv2D layer had padding set as “valid”, which mitigates the risk of overfitting and results in smaller feature maps, thus, focusing on most informative features [24]. Furthermore, after each Conv2D layer, ReLu activation (Rectified linear unit) and MaxPooling layer was applied. ReLu activation introduces non-linearity in the model by zeroing all negative feature values which avoids vanishing gradient problem effectively while MaxPooling reduces the spatial dimension of the feature map thereby lowering the computational load [25,26]. The design choice for kernel size, stride and pooling parameters were chosen to balance feature extraction, spatial resolution control and computational efficiency. For instance, larger kernel size (5x5) in earlier layers captured broader information while smaller kernels (3x3) in later layers focused on finer details [27]. CNN architecture is visualized in Figure 3.

Fig 3: CNN Model Architecture

Additionally, Batch Normalization was applied in alternate layers, between Conv2D and ReLu activation, to improve generalization and training stability [28]. Then, the convolutional feature maps were transformed into a 1D vector using flattening, for dense layer classification [29]. Again, to avoid overfitting, a dropout layer of 0.5 rate was employed, which regularizes training by randomly setting a fraction of input units to zero [30]. At the end of the model, a fully connected dense layer with softmax activation was applied for 3

class classification tasks, which gave class probabilities as output [31]. Lastly, the total trainable parameters were 122,275, making the model suitable for real-time inference on edge devices.

For training, Adam Optimizer with a learning rate of 0.001 and sparse categorical cross-entropy loss was used for efficient multiclass classification. Adam optimizer is known for handling sparse gradient and noisy data effectively while training deep learning models [32]. Training was conducted with a batch size of 50 for 15 epochs, and the results were visualized in Figure 4, which shows a gradual and smooth increase in training accuracy and decrease in training loss, while sudden dips and peaks can be observed in validation accuracy and loss respectively. This suggests batch wise variations or overfitting in particular epochs due to the fact that image augmentation was applied on training dataset but not on validation dataset. However, it should be noted that final training accuracy and loss was similar to validation accuracy and loss, which rejects the notion of overfitting and rather promotes generalizability. This theory is further supported by test results which achieved 79% accuracy in comparison to 78% training accuracy and 77% validation accuracy.

Fig 4: Training and Validation Accuracy (Left), Training and Validation Loss (Right)

To further refine the predictions, ROC based thresholding was applied for each class based on maximizing TPR-FPR [33]. This post processing step, improved F1 scores (precision-sensitivity balance) for normal and viral class, overall accuracy and Dice coefficient (sensitivity-specificity balance) by approximately 10%, while increasing Bacterial F1 score by 1%, showing significant enhancement in class wise balance.

2.4 Random Forest - Divya

The random forest method works as an ensemble approach in machine learning and is used in many applications of classification, particularly proving its potential for classifying severe pneumonia cases [34]. This method uses a combination of decision tree predictors where each tree depends on the values of a random vector that has been sampled independently ensuring the same distribution of the trees across in the forest [35]. The generalizability error of a forest of tree classifiers is dependent on the strength of how each individual tree behaves and the respective correlation between them. It is also known for handling missing values and still retaining a reasonable accuracy across different applications, which has led to its prominence in machine learning research [35].

However, some constraints may affect random forests-the first of which is computational complexity-and another, perhaps, would be its interpretability/analysis as an extensive presence of trees sometimes can create the difficulty of analyzing the model, and its ability to perform could be affected if noisy or irrelevant features are present there [35]. Our Random Forest classifier was implemented to classify the data into three categories: normal, bacterial pneumonia, and viral pneumonia, to find out any meaningful pattern or trends.

To begin with, class weights were applied to the training dataset to mitigate the issue of class imbalance as observed in EDA, because sometimes one category is significantly overrepresented or one class being more frequent than others results in biasness being developed towards the majority values leading to a reduction in the predictive performance for the minority classes, which negatively impacts the generalizability of the model leading to poor prediction within underrepresented categories [36]. By ensuring balanced class representation during training, the model performance improves and leads to more robust and unbiased classification in our model.

Furthermore, it is notable that grayscale conversion is commonly used for Random Forest-based image processing because it eliminates any unnecessary colour information that might not be a good indicator for classification [37]. The theory behind this is based on the

fact that Random Forest uses pixel intensity distributions rather than colour variations, therefore grayscale conversion allows a more uniform representation which ensures that the model focuses on structural and textural features as well rather than solely relying on the colours itself [37]. This technique also enables the model to identify and capture significant contrast differences, edge details and shape patterns crucial for medical imaging classification tasks [37].

2.5 Transfer Learning CNN using ResNet50 - Nahiyen

This classification model utilized a transfer learning approach centered on the ResNet50 architecture to perform 3-class classification of pediatric chest X-ray images into Normal, Bacterial, and Viral pneumonia categories. The ResNet50 model has a deep convolutional neural network architecture made of 50 layers and is well known for its use of residual learning to overcome vanishing gradient issues common in deep networks [38]. Currently, it has become a widely adopted model for transfer learning applications due to its depth and ability to generalize well across domains [39]. Transfer learning refers to leveraging pre-trained models on large datasets such as ImageNet and fine-tuning them for specific tasks, thereby reducing training time and improving performance in cases of limited domain-specific data [40]. In the context of pneumonia classification, transfer learning with ResNet50 has shown notable success, particularly in pediatric datasets where clear distinctions between normal, bacterial, and viral pneumonia can be subtle and complex [41]. However, standard implementations of ResNet50 can lead to challenges such as overfitting on small datasets and computational inefficiency due to its depth and parameter count [42].

To address these limitations, our model had a specific design which mitigated inherent constraints of biomedical imaging. Firstly, input images were resized to (224, 224, 3) and passed through the ResNet50 model with frozen weights to output a 2048-dimensional feature vector for each image, capturing relevant spatial and semantic information. These extracted features serve as the foundation for subsequent classification tasks which were performed by a convolutional neural network (CNN). The processing of freezing the base layers during initial training preserves the generalized image features learned from ImageNet and focused

training only on the top classification layers, which is a common technique in transfer learning to prevent overfitting on small medical datasets [40]. This technique also makes the overall system computationally efficient and suitable for real-time or low-resource deployment environments. The decision to use this pipeline reflects the goal to develop a robust, interpretable, and resource-aware solution for pediatric pneumonia detection from chest X-ray images.

3. EVALUATION

The following tables and figures highlight the results for three classification models- CNN Model, Random Forest Classification and CNN Model using Resnet 50. The performance of each model was assessed using precision, recall, F1 score, accuracy, macro Dice coefficient, and ROC-AUC curves.

Table 1: Classification Report for CNN model

Type	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	Support(%)	F1 Score (%)
Normal	96	82	234	89
Bacterial	85	95	242	90
Viral	78	80	148	79

Table 2: Classification Report for Random Forest Machine Learning Model

Type	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	Support(%)	F1 Score (%)
Normal	83	94	270	88
Bacterial	79	84	508	81
Viral	66	48	269	55

Table 3: Classification Report for CNN Model using Resnet50

Type	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	Support(%)	F1 Score (%)
Normal	80	97	242	88
Bacterial	99	74	234	85
Viral	77	80	148	78.8

Table 4: Comparing the overall performance through accuracy and dice coefficient for three different models

Type of Model	Overall Accuracy(%)	Macro Dice Coefficient
CNN Model	87	0.8602
Random Forest Classification	77.45	0.7494
CNN using Resnet 50	85	0.8420

Fig 8: Confusion Matrix for CNN Model

Fig 5: ROC-AUC Curve for CNN Model

Fig 9: Confusion Matrix for CNN - ResNet Model

Fig 6: ROC-AUC Curve for CNN - ResNet Model

Fig 10: Confusion Matrix for Random Forest Model

Fig 7: ROC-AUC Curve for Random Forest Model

As seen in Table 4, the CNN model demonstrated the highest overall accuracy of 87% with a macro Dice coefficient of 0.8602, closely followed by the ResNet50 model at 85% accuracy and a Dice coefficient of 0.8420, while the Random Forest model lagged behind with 77.45% accuracy and 0.7494 Dice. Furthermore, Table 1, Table 2 and Table 3 depicts that the CNN and ResNet50 models also exhibited strong class-specific precision and recall, particularly in the detection of Bacterial

pneumonia, where the CNN scored 85% precision and 95% recall, and ResNet50 achieved 99% precision and 74% recall. In contrast, the Random Forest model showed weaknesses, especially in detecting Viral pneumonia, with a notably low recall of 48%, which raises concerns about its sensitivity to this class. These performance disparities are further reflected in the ROC-AUC values (Figure 5-7), where both the CNN and ResNet50 models achieved values above 0.87 across all classes, while the Random Forest model showed a drop in AUC for Bacterial (0.88) and Viral (0.80) pneumonia despite scoring 0.98 for Normal cases.

These outcomes can be attributed to the inherent characteristics of each model architecture. The ResNet50 model leverages transfer learning, a technique that fine-tunes deep networks pre-trained on large datasets like ImageNet for domain-specific tasks, effectively addressing issues such as vanishing gradients and overfitting common in deep learning models trained from scratch [43]. Its residual connections and hierarchical feature extraction enable the model to generalize better across classes, even with limited labeled medical data, thus reducing training time and enhancing performance [43]. The CNN model, while requiring more computational tuning, still proved robust due to its custom architecture and class weighting strategies that addressed imbalances in the dataset. On the other hand, although Random Forest is known for its effectiveness in tabular data and certain image classification tasks [44], its reliance on grayscale intensity patterns may fail to capture the complex spatial and textural cues present in chest X-rays, resulting in reduced performance, particularly for minority classes.

Despite its lower recall, the Random Forest model maintains value due to its simplicity and transparency, making it a useful baseline or supplementary tool. In contrast, the deep learning models, especially with ResNet50, provide a powerful, scalable solution, aligning with current literature that endorses transfer learning for medical image classification [45]. However, limitations such as potential domain mismatch in pretrained models and the risk of overfitting when fine-tuning on small datasets must be acknowledged. Overall, our findings support the adoption of CNNs with transfer learning for robust, high-accuracy classification in pediatric pneumonia detection, while also highlighting

the need for class balance, interpretability, and model tuning in clinical machine learning applications.

4. CONCLUSION

In summary, our comparative evaluation of three machine learning models - Random Forest, CNN, and ResNet50 with transfer learning, highlights the superior performance of deep learning methods, particularly the ResNet50 architecture, in classifying pediatric pneumonia from chest X-rays. These findings align with existing literature that demonstrates the effectiveness of transfer learning in medical image analysis, due to its ability to generalize from large-scale pre-trained networks and reduce training time. While the CNN model also showed promise, particularly with class rebalancing techniques, the ResNet50 model's hierarchical feature extraction and residual learning mechanisms led to the highest accuracy and F1 scores. The Random Forest classifier, despite being computationally efficient and interpretable, underperformed in capturing the spatial and textural nuances of X-ray images, an outcome consistent with studies emphasizing the limitations of classical methods on complex imaging tasks.

Furthermore, in future work, we propose the integration of Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) to augment training data and improve generalization in low-data regimes, as demonstrated by Frid-Adar et al. [46]. Additionally, incorporating explainability frameworks such as Grad-CAM or SHAP could enhance clinical trust and model transparency. Expanding the dataset, optimizing hyperparameters, and employing hybrid architectures that combine classical and deep learning features may further boost diagnostic accuracy and clinical utility.

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